

Geometric place footprints and the modifiable areal unit problem

René Westerholt*¹

¹Department of Spatial Planning, TU Dortmund University

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Summary

When studying places in GIScience, we often analyse their geometric footprints. Sketch maps, for instance, can be used to capture sense of place, place identity, or place dependence. This paper examines the relationship between place footprints and the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP). Unlike polygons such as postcode areas, place footprints inherently relate to the underlying places themselves. Considering the MAUP aspects of location, scale, shape, and aggregation, I argue that the MAUP remains relevant, as place footprints are stochastic candidates of geometric representations and thus inherently modifiable – not in relation to another process, but in a self-referential manner.

KEYWORDS: place, footprint, sketch maps, spatial analysis, modifiable areal unit problem.

1 Introduction

Sketch maps understood as outcomes of “participants sketching onto aerial images, base maps, or tracing paper” (Boschmann and Cubbon, 2014, p. 239) are common objects of study in GIScience (e.g. Manivannan et al., 2022; Schwering et al., 2022). They are also frequently used to geometrically map the concept of place (for an overview, see Brown et al., 2020). The latter is not naturally amenable to reductionism without largely sacrificing the underlying object of study. Still, sketch maps are given to us as georeferenced geometric footprints of more complex meaningful places. The term place can thereby be understood in different ways, depending on the school of thought that one adheres to. For example, a humanistic-geographical approach would locate place in the direct experience of the pre-reflective lifeworld, where it is characterised by underlying essences (Seamon and Larsen, 2020), while a post-structuralist (e.g. drawing on assemblage theory) would follow a non-essentialist notion of place as a constantly evolving constellation that gives rise to emergent properties (Dovey, 2020). Regardless of the chosen conceptualisation, reducing a place to its geometric footprint is likely not a deterministic act. For instance, the aforementioned evolving constellations as per assemblage theory are never fixed and it is therefore a matter of chance which spatiotemporally contingent place constellation is precisely depicted in a footprint. The humanistic geographer may likewise argue that footprints are always construed in the light of certain lived

*rene.westerholt@tu-dortmund.de

engagements and are therefore inherently stochastic. It thus seems reasonable to assume that people have several candidates for such footprint representations. When asked to externalise one of them, the result is not *the* footprint, but *one of many possible* such footprints. This short paper discusses an aspect relevant for the spatial analysis of geometric place footprints that is related to their probabilistic nature as outlined above: their relation to selected aspects of the well-known modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP; Openshaw, 1984), which pertains to polygons employed in data aggregation. Considering that in spatial analysis polygons are often imposed externally as containers and only for the purpose of analysis, for example when using postcode or census areas, the guiding question is: To what extent and how are self-provided, bottom-up geometric place footprints influenced by the MAUP?

2 Positioning and scale

In the case of mere aggregation polygons like postcode areas that are often lacking a direct generative connection to some process under investigation, both their positioning and their scale are frequently decoupled from the processes analysed through them. The task is then to make sure that both parameters closely match those of the latter, which is a theoretical rather than an empirical issue and thus not an easy task to accomplish (Wolf et al., 2021). However, for bottom-up footprints as considered here, the polygons are the result of the externalisation process of translating places into geometries and thus possess a partially intrinsic connection to the places they represent. In terms of the MAUP, the positioning of the polygons and their scale are thus no longer subject to methodological decisions of the researcher, but properties of the geometric representation of places. The only way in which such polygons may still be subject to researchers' decisions is indirectly, through the design of data collection campaigns. Positioning and scale of the polygons are thus not arbitrary in relation to the subject under investigation and are only modifiable in the sense that they are the result of a random process in which someone at a particular time, in a particular situation, and with a particular intention geometrically sketches their meaningful places.

The difference between polygons such as postcode areas and those such as geometric place footprints, then, lies in the *source* of modifiability. But what are the meanings of modifiable geometric scale and location in relation to some underlying place? For responding to this question, we shall consider an example like comparing an elongated coastline polygon (Figure 1a) with a small-scale city-centre polygon (Figure 1b), both mapped by Lisbon residents¹. The person who sketched the coastline polygon is unlikely to have experienced the entire coastline at once, but only sporadically and different parts of it. Nevertheless, the coastline was presented as a semantically coherent place in terms of some underlying idea. The inner-city polygon also represents an idea of a place that is likely not constantly experienced in its entirety and where several meaningful experiences have been made. Further, while the northern end of the coastline polygon appears to be fairly well defined (ending near the iconic Vasco da Gama Bridge), the footprint shows a diffuse southern end. This could indicate that the person who made the sketch might have a closer relationship or more frequent interactions with and in the northern part of the area. It is also possible that the engagements in the southern part occurred longer ago compared to the northern end or that no such direct

¹Both polygons reflect meaningful places and come from a survey introduced in Westerholt and Acedo (2024).

(a) Shoreline footprint

(b) City centre footprint

Figure 1: Two examples of geometric place footprints sketched by Lisbon residents. The footprints represent personally important places and originate from a web mapping-supported participatory mapping exercise, supplemented by a survey to operationalise sense of place (for methodological details, see Westerholt and Acedo, 2024). Road data and building footprints copyrighted OpenStreetMap contributors and available from <https://www.openstreetmap.org>. The coastline data used originates from Eurostat.

experiences were ever made first hand. This demonstrates that the geometric footprints, despite being geometrically very different, both represent momentary mental condensates of a series of past place engagements, including the resulting place-making processes, and the ways in which those were combined into coherent mental images and then translated into geometric forms. My response to this is twofold: (i) there is likely no singular and deterministic mechanism that translates the outlined complexity into geometric footprints, and (ii) the importance of geometric scale and the precise location of the footprints should not be overstated in their spatial analysis, as these are not precise mappings of the underlying places. The scale and location of place footprints are thus indeed highly modifiable in the sense of the MAUP, but for entirely different reasons than those of postcode and census areas.

3 Aggregation and shape

The MAUP has to do with polygons utilised for aggregation. The way in which place footprints act as aggregating units becomes clear if we consider the nature of what they represent, that is, of place. Regardless of the choice of any specific conceptualisation from human geography, place differs from (geometric) space in that it resists reductionism and embraces the view that ‘the whole is more than the sum of its parts’ (Seamon, 2024). Although the place footprints in themselves suggest a reductionism, we should thus bear in mind the nature of place that we ultimately want to learn about through them. This implies that the polygons are indeed aggregating (not just amassing): experiences, materialities, activities, social relations, feelings, memories – in short: what Edward Casey referred to as ‘gathering’ (Casey, 1996). The polygons themselves are therefore to

be regarded as results of the interplay of these many different components, which has had its effect on how someone has externalised a place geometrically. This interplay is a process and, when considered in conjunction with the stochastic nature of the footprints, this means that the intensity of this interplay is variable both within (as we have seen in the examples above) and across different footprints. The aggregation capacity of place footprints is thus not about combining what is physically enclosed by them. Rather, the aggregation concerns lived experiences and takes place before someone translates a place into a geometry. The aggregation therefore already feeds into the translation process from place to footprint. Sometimes, place footprints also act as containers in a traditional sense, for example when they are used to associate a place with something else, as we did in a Lisbon study and in relation to urban amenities (Westerholt et al., 2022). In such cases, the polygons serve as containers for the aggregation of something else in the classic MAUP sense. In doing so, we should not only consider the types of modifiability described above, but also the fact that the sketching of a boundary around an object like a place, which may not actually involve strict boundaries (see Winter and Freksa, 2012), implies arbitrariness along the contour line. In other words, the ‘correct’ polygon does not and possibly cannot exist beyond candidate status.

4 Conclusions

The brief discussion above shows that it is important to consider the MAUP *in relation to* something and not as an isolated issue. Postcode areas, for example, are not arbitrary or modifiable per se. It is only when they are used in conjunction with processes for which they were never designed that they become problematic. When it comes to the bottom-up generated geometric sketch maps for representing places, this intuitively does not seem to be a problem as the polygons – in contrast to the postcode areas – are endogenous. However, I argue that the MAUP is effective as the polygons are the results of a translation process that cannot map the underlying places one-to-one and are therefore subject to variation. I therefore suggest that we need to bear in mind the *source of modifiability* in a meaningful way, otherwise we might erroneously assume that bottom-up polygons, like place footprints, are unaffected by the MAUP. What exactly this means in practice requires further methodological research. However, considering the complexity of the source of modifiability outlined above and the difficulty of accessing its origins, a mixed approach incorporating methods from human geography could be fruitful. The discussion in this paper is related to the recent general interest in place in GIScience (Mocnik, 2022; Tang and Painho, 2021; Hamzei et al., 2020; Purves et al., 2019; Merschdorf and Blaschke, 2018) and complements my own previous research on the topic of geometric place footprints (e.g. Westerholt and Acedo, 2024; Westerholt, 2019). This work also ties into arguments offered by Mei-Po Kwan (Kwan, 2018a,b, 2021), who argues for moving beyond simple geometric neighbourhood concepts when studying environmental exposures in health geography, showing that the discussion of moving beyond reductionist geometries is of broad and current relevance.

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Biography

René Westerholt is Juniorprofessor and head of the Spatial Modelling Lab at the Department of Spatial Planning at TU Dortmund University (Germany). His research interests include urban analytics, formalising space and place, and spatial statistics.

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